

Skills 4 eosc

D6.3 “Top 10 FAIR Data Things” in Artificial Intelligence & Published recommendations on FAIR data in Health Technology

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Deliverable Abstract

This is a deliverable of two parts: a “Top 10 FAIR Data Things” in Artificial Intelligence and FAIR Data for Health Technology (HT). While there have been efforts to implement the FAIR principles in specific fields applying Artificial Intelligence (AI), there is a dearth of clear low-threshold, cross-discipline guidelines. FAIR practices, could benefit AI research and researchers e.g., through setting benchmarks for model development and interpretation, enabling reuse in research and education and leading to better collaboration. Using the Delphi Technique we engaged the AI research community to create a “Top 10 FAIR Data Things in AI”, intended to be a simple-to-follow guide and the foundation for more nuanced strategies as needs arise. Regarding FAIR practices in HT, there is no ready community, and negligible literature. We surveyed researchers and data professionals to obtain a snapshot of current awareness and practice regarding the FAIR principles. Here we present a preliminary discussion on the issues, intended to stimulate discussions in other areas of HT research, supporting FAIR data practices more widely across this domain and the focus of a relevant network being initiated as part of this task.

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TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

<i>Terminology/Acronym</i>	<i>Definition</i>
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AI Model	An AI model is a mathematical framework that enables AI capabilities. It's trained on data to recognize patterns and make predictions or decisions. AI models apply different algorithms to relevant data inputs to achieve the tasks, or output, they have been programmed for. Examples of AI models are: Decision trees, Statistical networks like Bayesian Networks, Neural Networks (CNN, RNN, Transformers used in LLMs etc.), NLP, GenAI models
AI System	A machine-based system that is designed to operate with varying levels of autonomy and that may exhibit adaptiveness after deployment, and that, for explicit or implicit objectives, infers, from the input it receives, how to generate outputs such as predictions, content, recommendations, or decisions that can influence physical or virtual environments (EU AI Act, 2024)
BoF	Birds of a Feather
DL	Deep Learning
FAIR4ML	FAIR for Machine Learning Interest Group (RDA)
HPC	High Performance Computing
HT Research Data	Health Technology research data can be regarded as “data which is collected, generated, analysed, and (re-)used during the design, testing, and assessment of new technological devices and systems developed to solve a health problem and / or improve quality of lives” (task working definition).

IIT	Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia
KIT ML	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology
ML	Machine Learning
ML Model	An ML model is one type of AI model. It is a program that can find patterns or make decisions from a previously unseen dataset. A machine learning model can perform such tasks as a results of being 'trained' with a large dataset. During training, the machine learning algorithm is optimized to find certain patterns or outputs from the dataset, depending on the task. The output of this process - often a computer program with specific rules and data structures - is called a machine learning model.
Pipeline	A series of interconnected data processing and modelling steps designed to automate, standardise and streamline the process of building, training, evaluating and deploying machine learning models.
SciLifeLab	Science for Life Laboratory, Sweden
TEF	Testing and Experimentation Facility for Health and Robotics
TUD	Delft University of Technology

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1 Executive summary

The purpose of this deliverable is twofold. To create a “Top 10” Recommendations for implementation of the FAIR principles in AI (section 3), and to report efforts in establishing the state of FAIR data practices in Health Technology (HT) research and bringing people together to discuss these topics (section 4). The aim of both these outputs is to stimulate the uptake of FAIR practices in these domains by working with the researchers, data professionals and other relevant persons in the respective communities.

Since the publication of the FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship in 2016, efforts have continued to be made to apply these principles of Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability in different domains to varying degrees with varying levels of success. With respect to AI however, the challenges are different, perhaps more complex, as large datasets together with software, specific operational environments and hardware, etc., are involved. There are many benefits to applying the FAIR principles to processes and components of AI, however, there are challenges to their implementation, including a lack of clear simple to follow guidelines, examples and metrics for comparing models. Skills4EOSC recognises these needs and the importance of working with the AI research community to develop and agree on low-threshold ways to apply the FAIR principles to AI research. The intention of the “Top 10” is just that - to be a fundamental simple to follow guide, which can help to make applying FAIR to AI easier on a daily basis, adopted and adapted to suit more specific instances as researchers and data professionals may need.

Health Technology presents greater challenges, as there is no ready community, and negligible literature mentioning both “FAIR” and “Health Technology”. A distinct lack of guidelines exists. Here we present a preliminary discussion on the issues, including challenges encountered during the task, and ideas which we hope will serve as the basis for further discussions in other areas of Health Technology research, supporting FAIR data practices more widely across this domain. As clarified in the text, the Health Technology section is necessarily more exploratory, and should be

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understood as an initial mapping of the landscape rather than a fully developed framework.

2 Introduction

For both thematic areas (Artificial Intelligence and Health Technology), we engaged communities or individuals: researchers and data professionals, and in addition, in the case of Health Technology, healthcare practitioners. We strove to have wide distribution among participants and collaborators with respect to geography, organisation, job title and career level. For both areas, we utilised surveys via the EU Survey Tool, holding several consultative discussions with contributors and participants before and after these surveys.

It is important to note that, for the purposes of this deliverable, the distinction between “health data” and “health technology data” is based on a working definition developed within the task. While this definition serves as a useful foundation for discussion, it has not yet been broadly validated by the wider research community. Further consultation and community engagement will be necessary to refine and formalise this definition over time.

This work followed work done in Task 6.1 (Mapping of Existing Professional Networks), which identified over 325 Open Science, Data Steward and AI communities and networks across 24 European countries. While the conception of how work should proceed started earlier, including literature reviews, it was subsequent to D6.1 that we began to identify potential collaborators and to envision engagement with them. We focused first on working with the AI community (Task 6.3.3a), as this is already well-established, transferring the insights gained to work in the Health Technology task (6.3.3b), which is not a well-defined area with no existing community with which to collaborate. Indeed, there were two aspects to T6.3.3b which went hand in hand: create a network for those interested in FAIR data in Health Technology, and with this network, evaluate and recommend ways to implement the FAIR principles in Health Technology research. Creating the FAIR for Health Technology Network therefore followed on from results in Task 6.2 Development of Starter Kits for Professional Networks. Challenges were encountered in the creation of this network (and therefore evaluation

and recommendation of FAIR practices) and these will be elaborated on below. Overall, work on Tasks 6.3.3a and 6.3.3b started in February 2023 and the deliverable was handed in for internal review at the start of May 2025.

The report is structured as follows. In section 3, we report the methodology and results regarding the “Top10” in AI. We also discuss challenges encountered along the way, as well as any activities in which we participated, and our main collaborations. As the study was a multi-stage one, interim results will be presented and discussed at the appropriate place in the methodology. We also report on the final stage of the study during which a subsection of participants discussed the “Top 10”, other practices and relevant topics to enrich the results and suggest further development of guidelines. We close section 3 with a brief discussion of the next steps, which include co-creation, further refinement, and uptake in the relevant communities.

In section 4 we report an investigation into the current state of FAIR practices in Health Technology and the development of a network initiative for those interested in this topic. As mentioned in section 1, several challenges were encountered in the execution of this task; these are discussed in section 4.1. This will be followed by the methodology, which has common aspects with the “Top 10” in AI, but took place over one stage only. Thus there are discreet sections for the methodology and results. Similarly to section 3, section 4 will close with a brief discussion of next steps, including in this case, the FAIR Data in Health Technology Network Initiative.

3 Top 10 FAIR Data Things in Artificial Intelligence

The goal of the task is to address the existing dearth of low-threshold, simple to follow, cross-discipline guidelines that would support FAIR implementation in AI. Therefore we adopted the following approach. We focused on machine learning (ML) AI models, as these are widely used and presented good opportunities to collaborate with ongoing well-aligned efforts (see below). Further, we do not distinguish between supervised, unsupervised or reinforcement learning. We do not discuss or explicitly link any FAIR principle or practice to specific aspects of more complex models such as deep learning/neural networks. Additionally, although we do not talk about generative models or natural language processing models, the approach in our study and the results can be extrapolated and applied to these types of models and the process through which they were created. Thus for the remainder of the report we will refer to ML/AI models.

The method agreed upon as best for the task was the Delphi Technique (Biderbeck et al., 2021). Some members of the task team had had previous experience using this method (Cobey et al., 2022), and it presented a way to achieve credible and systematic consensus from our target community. However, to ensure methodological robustness, an extensive desk research of alternative methodologies was carried out. The Delphi method was ultimately deemed most appropriate due to its iterative nature, structured feedback, flexibility, and effectiveness in achieving consensus among geographically dispersed experts.

3.1 The Delphi Technique

The Delphi technique has been used across many disciplines including technology, engineering, education, business, healthcare and medicine. It is a systematic and iterative method designed to gather expert consensus and insights for topics areas in which there is limited information (Fig.1). The

number of questionnaire rounds can differ depending on the particular study.

Fig. 1 - Illustration of the Delphi Technique (Humphrey-Murto et al., 2017 and illustrations by storyset)

The project team conducted a 2-Round study (survey-based) followed by an Online Meeting aimed to get additional feedback on the selected practices from the respondents (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2 - Schematic representation of Delphi rounds and Online Meeting

3.2 Delphi Study Preparation Phase

The preparation phase involved an in-depth desk research and literature review, preliminary identification of FAIR practices relevant to ML/AI, identification and engagement of experts, and finalization of the Delphi questionnaire (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3 - Schematic overview of the Delphi preparation phase

3.2.1 Desk Research & Literature Review

The initial phase of the project involved desk research and a comprehensive literature review to scope current FAIR practices in ML/AI. This included reviewing methodologies relevant to carrying out the study and identifying suitable tools and platforms for this. Key resources were systematically collected, categorised, and made publicly accessible through a dedicated Zotero library available [here](#).

3.2.2 Expert Identification and Engagement

Identification of potential experts began with mapping relevant research groups, laboratories, and facilities at IIT, TU Delft, KIT and other project partners engaged in ML/AI research.

In March 2023, the RDA [FAIR4ML](#) IG (FAIR for Machine Learning Interest Group) was identified as a potential collaborator because of their ongoing work towards a white paper on FAIR Practices in Machine Learning. The “Top 10” task team recognised the similarities across our objectives and the benefits of leveraging the expertise of the global FAIR4ML community, which presently has around 140 members. FAIR4ML co-chairs accepted a proposal for collaboration between Skills4EOSC and FAIR4ML. The collaboration with FAIR4ML yielded early results with the publication of the report *Lifecycle for FAIR Machine Learning* (Castro et al., 2023).

Lernende Systeme: Germany's Platform for Artificial Intelligence	Mathematical Research Data Initiative	Network of National Centres of Excellence for AI Research	NFDI for Data Science and Artificial Intelligence	The Artificial Intelligence Section
NFDI Consortium for Business, Economic and Related Data	ARCHIMEDES	HPC Competence Center Greece	Confederation of Laboratories for Artificial Intelligence Research in Europe	Coordination and Support for National Competence Centres on a European Level
European Network of AI Excellence Centres	The European Laboratory for Learning and Intelligent Systems	Women in AI & Robotics	TERATEC	CeADAR: Ireland's Centre for Applied AI
Irish Centre for High-End Computing	Big Data Association	Italian Association for Artificial Intelligence	Artificial Intelligence Netherlands	Innovation Center for Artificial Intelligence
Netherlands Artificial Intelligence Coalition	Nordic Artificial Intelligence Network	North Macedonia EuroHPC Competence Center	Norwegian Artificial Intelligence Network for Europe	Norwegian Artificial Intelligence Research Consortium
AI Hub	Artificial Intelligence Research Alliance	EuroCC Spain	Network of Excellence in Data Technologies	The Spanish Supercomputing Network
Competence Network for Artificial Intelligence	Swiss Academy of Engineering Sciences	Swiss AI Research Overview Platform	Swiss Group for Artificial Intelligence and Cognitive Science	The Swiss HPC Service Provider Community
Artificial Intelligence Innovation Network	EuroCC@UK	Hartree National Centre for Digital Innovation	Museums + Artificial Intelligence Network	National centre for AI
	The Alan Turing Institute	Distributed Research Utilising Advanced Computing		

Fig. 4 - List of the AI communities extracted from D6.1

Additional experts were identified from existing AI networks and communities listed in [Skills4EOSC D6.1](#) (Buss et al., 2023). Contact points within these communities were actively engaged to ensure broad and representative expert participation. Fig 4 shows a list of the AI communities extracted from D6.1 that were identified and contacted. In January 2023, a

dedicated workshop involving IIT researchers was held, aimed at promoting project objectives and collaboratively defining a comprehensive list of potential participants.

Finally, a list of international individual experts was compiled, as well as a list of contact persons from different AI networks and communities. Emails were then sent out to gather expressions of interest. An email with the survey link was subsequently sent out only to those experts that confirmed their agreement to participate in the study. The survey was promoted via Skills4EOSC project communication channels.

3.2.3 Selecting the Recommendations for Round 1

Based on the literature review, a preliminary list of recommendations of FAIR for ML was drafted for Round 1 of the survey. Members of the FAIR4ML community provided feedback on these items. After incorporating this feedback – a final list of 20 recommended practices was prepared for expert evaluation in Round 1 ([Appendix I](#)). This process included refining the preliminary list by removing redundancies, overlaps, and items not strictly related to the FAIR principles, such as those related to more generic “fairness” aspects. The formulation of the items was improved to ensure clarity and relevance.

3.2.4 Selecting the platform for the study

Various survey platforms (external and internal) were evaluated based on criteria such as security, openness, cost-effectiveness, and user-friendliness. The [EUSurvey](#) platform emerged as the most suitable platform, offering a user-friendly interface accessible across diverse devices, customisable features, data security, and alignment with European standards. This platform has also been used across Skills4EOSC tasks, including others in WP6.

3.3 Delphi Study Execution Phase

3.3.1 Delphi Round 1

3.3.1.1 Survey Contents

Participants were invited via personalised invitations to complete an online survey hosted on [EUSurvey](#). The data collected were managed in accordance with relevant regulations and policies. The survey included three structured sections:

1. Participant Information

Capturing demographic data, institutional affiliation, career stage and professional roles.

2. List of 20 practices on which to vote

In this section, participants rated each practice using a 5-point Likert scale from (1='Not Recommended' to 5= 'Strongly Recommended'), with additional space provided for comments or reasons for their answer (Fig. 5).

* 1. ML/AI models should be trained on FAIR data. ⓘ

To increase FAIRness of an ML/AI model, training data should be thoroughly documented and made FAIR themselves.

1	2	3	4	5	I don't know
---	---	---	---	---	--------------

This field is required.

(Optional) Provide comments and/or reasons for your choice.

* 2. Globally Unique Persistent Identifiers should be assigned to ML/AI models and included in their metadata. ⓘ

For instance, a DOI should be assigned to the ML/AI model and its metadata to make it findable for both humans and machines via indexing in searchable resources. In the case of model updates, new identifiers must be generated to distinguish the updated versions from the original.

1	2	3	4	5	I don't know
---	---	---	---	---	--------------

This field is required.

Fig. 5 - Examples of practices in Round 1 (screenshot from EUSurvey)

3. Any recommended additional practices

In this section participants were invited to suggest any additional practices not included in the initial list of 20 (Fig. 6).

In this part of the survey, you can optionally recommend up to 5 additional practices that were not listed in the previous part.

Additional practice 1. Please provide a short description for this practice:

Additional practice 2. Please provide a short description for this practice:

Additional practice 3. Please provide a short description for this practice:

Fig. 6 - Any recommended additional practices (screenshot from EUSurvey)

Completion time

Survey completion was tested within the project team, resulting in an estimated participant engagement time of approximately 15-20 minutes.

3.3.1.2 Timeline

The survey was conducted from July to September 2024.

3.3.1.3 Participants

For the first round, 183 individual invitations were sent and representatives of 43 AI networks were contacted. 84 experts confirmed participation, of which, 67 eventually completed the survey (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7 - Round 1 invitations and participants

The participant pool was diverse, including experts from 15 different countries, though most were from Europe. A variety of interdisciplinary perspectives were also represented (Fig. 8).

Fig. 8 - Location of participants. (Powered by Bing)

Participants were distributed across multiple career stages and professional roles, enhancing the depth and diversity of expert opinion (Fig. 9 and 10).

Fig. 9 - Distribution of participants across career stages

Fig.10 - Analysis of roles in different categories

3.3.1.4 Analysis and Results

Consensus for each recommended practice was defined as at least 60% of responses converging on a single point of the Likert scale. Practices achieving a strong recommendation (score of 5) were automatically included in the Top 10 list. Six practices met the threshold for 'Strongly Recommended', another six were identified as borderline, and eight recommendations were less favourably evaluated. Analyses of the consensus on the voted practices and comments by participants were conducted in R Studio (Rstudio version 2022.07.0, R version 4.2.1). The code used to perform the analyses will be shared via Zenodo, together with the anonymised dataset.

3.3.2 Delphi Round 2

3.3.2.1 Participants

All 67 Round 1 respondents were invited to participate in Round 2, with 54 eventually participating.

3.3.2.2 Survey Contents

The survey consisted of 2 main sections (see [Appendix II](#)):

1. Practices to be re-voted on from Round 1 (6 practices)

The six recommendations that fell just short of consensus in Round 1 were included in round 2 to enable participants to reconsider their position (Fig. 11). Definitions of these recommendations were further improved and refined based on comments of participants and literature.

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* Practice N.1: ML/AI models should be trained on FAIR data.

Whenever possible, to increase FAIRness of a ML/AI model, training data should be FAIR themselves, ensuring they are machine-actionable and thoroughly documented, as a pre-requisite for data quality. Using FAIR data to train models ensures higher reproducibility, increases reliability, trustworthiness, and transparency. We recall that FAIR does not mean "open" (e.g. sensitive datasets can be FAIR, without being open).

This field is required.

(Optional) Provide comments and/or reasons for your choice.

* Practice N.2: Globally Unique Persistent Identifiers should be assigned to ML/AI models and included in their metadata.

For instance, a DOI (or other type of globally persistent and unique identifier) should be assigned to the ML/AI model to make it findable for both humans and machines via indexing in searchable resources: this would increase the model's findability. In the case of model updates, new identifiers could be generated to distinguish the updated versions from the original.

(Optional) Provide comments and/or reasons for your choice.

Fig. 11 – Examples of round 1 practices for re-voting (EUSurvey screenshot)

2. Voting of six newly formulated recommendations derived from qualitative feedback in Round 1.

These new items were clearly articulated for consistent interpretation and evaluated using the same Likert scale as in Round 1 (Fig. 12).

* Practice A.1: References to all datasets (including versioning) used for training, validation, and testing of the ML/AI model must be included in the ML/AI model's metadata, via their Global Persistent and Unique Identifiers.

Include PIDs for each dataset in the model's metadata.

This field is required.

(Optional) Provide comments and/or reasons for your choice.

* Practice A.2: Model's metadata should include all information needed to fully reproduce the results, including (but not limited to) parameters like random number generator seed, hardware specifications, etc.

To make the AI/ML model reproducible, you should include different details on metadata like: model parameters, training environment, training process, information on the dataset etc.

(Optional) Provide comments and/or reasons for your choice.

Fig. 12 – Examples of new recommendations based on suggestions in round 1 (EUSurvey screenshot)

3.3.2.3 Analysis and Results

The same consensus criteria from Round 1 were applied. Four practices reached consensus in Round 2, adding to the six practices from Round 1.

The resulting list of Top 10 practices for FAIR in ML/AI is shown in Fig. 13. The practices encompass all of the FAIR principles, as shown from the labels reported in Figure 13 beside each practice (as inferred by the task team). See [Appendix III](#) for full description of the Top 10 and in which round they reached consensus.

Fig. 13 - List of top 10 practices for FAIR implementation in AI/ML

Some practices relate more closely to the general principles, simply stating the need to apply them to the ML/AI model - seen as a comprehensive “digital

object”, whereas others elaborate on more domain-specific requirements. In many practices, (machine-actionable) metadata and documentation are mentioned, as key FAIR-ness enablers. One of the practice refers to ethics, underling the importance to researchers in considering ethical aspects in AI. The analysis of participants’ votes and comments from both rounds highlights that most are broadly acknowledged as essential for improving reusability, transparency, and interoperability. However, it also reveals a need to balance the perceived importance of a practice and its practical implementation effort, often due to a lack of shared standards and tools.

Assigning Globally Unique Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) (Practice *a* from **Appendix III**) is deemed essential for clear identification of the model used (or its adaptations) and version management, although a comment highlights that it is not always clear if the PID refers to the actual model or the metadata. Practice *c*, a related and more elaborated practice, would bring greater clarification.

Rich metadata (Practice *b*), crucial for documentation, transparency, and probably the most important requirement for intelligent reuse, is largely considered feasible and a must-have despite existing ambiguities in its definition and scope.

Implementing retrievable metadata through standardised protocols (Practice *c*) offers significant benefits for accessibility and interoperability; however, its feasibility is hindered by scalability issues (large models need specific protocols, a certain bandwidth for retrieval). This practice would appear to include practice *a*, however, practice *c* reflects accessibility more specifically targeted to ML/AI models, whereas practice *a* reflects Findability. Further, team also feels bound by the selected practices that were approved by experts and subsequently voted on by them, and it is expected that in public consultation and further co-creation, more refinement may take place.

Reporting evaluation metrics within metadata (Practice *d*) and documenting input/output data requirements (Practice *e*) are both critical for enhancing transparency and reproducibility, yet encounter feasibility challenges due to variability in standards and practices. In particular, community-backed

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standards about evaluation metrics or input data should be defined, although since a model can be applied to several different use-cases, some participants point out that the performance will vary depending on what the model is applied to.

Ensuring metadata utilises documented, accessible formats (Practice *f*) is strongly supported for a proper accessibility, but raises concerns regarding existing standards' suitability and machine-readability. The latter are highly desirable and should be standardised.

Qualified references within metadata (Practice *g*) are essential for reproducibility and actually running the model, feasible in practice with some effort (e.g., containerization), although it is very difficult to rely on standards related for example to libraries and dependencies to run a model. To avoid presenting overly complex metadata, some suggest documenting/shifting certain technical details - such as exact library versions or dependency specifications - within the model's codebase or associated environment definitions (e.g., requirements.txt, project.yaml). Clear licensing (Practice *h*) emerges as extremely important for fostering trust and clarifying legal aspects, though uncertainties specific to AI/ML contexts complicate practical implementation.

Ethical documentation (Practice *i*), although increasingly recognized as crucial, remains challenging due to significant gaps in current methodologies and complexities involved. The practice is perceived as very desirable, although the ethics' aspects span a wide range of aspects, not all linked to the FAIR principles.

Finally, clear deployment instructions (Practice *j*) are highly valued for practical reuse, generally feasible but influenced by domain-specific factors and the technical capabilities of the target audience (also, not all models need to be deployed or widely reused: in many cases they are used just for tests and analyses).

Glaringly absent from the Top is the first item presented in round 1 of the survey "ML/AI models should be trained on FAIR data". From participants comments on this practice, it is not that many of them did not believe in this

in principle, but found it onerous or even impractical to their work. Expanding on this, some felt that this might work in some experimental settings, but not all; that FAIRness of the model should not be dependent on FAIRness of the data; that machine actionable data may already include some FAIR principles and importantly, FAIR does not equal open, therefore being strictly bound to using FAIR data could significantly affect research in some areas. Many, however, felt that this practice should either be default, or aspired to, and it was not outrightly rejected, but missed the consensus threshold. The Top 10 represents what survey participants felt were the most basic, necessary and feasible practices that would enable FAIR in AI. However, as can be seen from the discussion on those items that did not reach consensus, a “Top 20” would include recommendations on transparency, dependencies, limitations, FAIR datasets, and community standards, supported to various extents. There is a wealth of material to reflect upon, adapt to different contexts, and leverage—useful for both researchers and repositories that index ML/AI models.

Therefore, practices that did not reach the threshold for being in the Top 10 showed mostly, according to the comments of participants, concerns about the lack of practical feasibility of implementation and the lack of standards or sustainability (the latter, for example, in using containerisation). Challenges were identified in the evolving nature of ML/AI standards, the lack of clear and universally adopted interoperability frameworks, and the complexity associated with ensuring long-term accessibility of metadata or deploying from dedicated repositories. The comments deemed not very realistic the enforcement of privacy regulations through metadata annotations, since they might vary from country to country. Practices such as platform-independent model representation and containerisation were recognised as beneficial but technically demanding, risking unnecessary complication for simpler models. Finally, the integration of ontologies and adherence to community reporting guidelines were seen as highly desirable but requiring substantial effort and coordination to realize effectively.

Please see [Appendix IV](#) for a list of those practices that did not reach consensus and in which round this occurred.

3.4 Community Discussion

3.4.1 Meeting Context and Objectives

A final online meeting was held on 31 January 2025 online via Zoom. This was to allow participants and task members to meet and to discuss FAIR implementation in AI, specifically the Top 10 and other practices presented for voting at one stage or another during the study. All 67 Delphi study participants were invited to take part. Although 17 responded positively, only five attending on the day.

The main objectives of the meeting were to:

- Present and recap the final list of FAIR practices resulted from the second round of the Delphi study;
- Facilitate an interactive session and collect structured feedback on the 10 practices using Mentimeter (<https://www.mentimeter.com/>)
- Engage the community in an open discussion to identify areas of agreements, concerns and opportunities for implementing the Top 10 and to further enrich the results.

3.4.2 Summary Mentimeter Discussion

Although, attendance was lower than expected, participants engaged well with useful qualitative discussions. Participant feedback was gathered through a series of structured questions using Mentimeter, a web-app that enables real-time voting and commenting. Each question addressed a key dimension of FAIR practices, such as relevance, applicability and perceived implementation. The Mentimeter discussion is presented below in detail, with questions, answers and comments. These questions were meant to contextualise the views of those participating in the discussion, with the understanding that they do not represent the entire study sample.

Question: What is your area of AI research?

Participants were asked about their area of expertise in AI research. The most popular areas were Machine Learning and Knowledge Representation (Fig. 14).

Fig. 14 - AI research areas of expertise among participants

Question: What is your area of AI application?

Responses showed that most people worked in environmental applications followed by healthcare applications, and acceleration of scientific research in general (Fig. 15).

Fig. 15 – Distribution of AI application areas

Question: Which of the Top 10 practices may be easier to implement?

Participants regarded assigning unique identifiers, providing rich and comprehensive metadata, and ensuring clear licensing as critical best practices in FAIR for ML/AI. Ethics considerations were considered the most challenging to implement (Fig. 16).

Fig. 16 – Top 10 practices: ease of implementation

Additional comments from respondents:

While structured data simplifies FAIR compliance, broader metadata implementation and agreement on the most important metadata to report remains challenging, often due to social and organizational barriers (understanding the benefit and finding time for proper implementation) rather than technical ones.

Question: Which of the Top 10 practices may be challenging to implement?

Emphasis was placed on the retrievability of AI models through persistent identifiers and the inclusion of ethical considerations in metadata,

underscoring a strong commitment to transparency and ethical responsibility in AI development. Also, including metadata about performance evaluation is seen as challenging (Fig. 17).

Fig. 17 – Top 10 practices: difficulty in implementation

Additional comments from respondents:

As in the previous question, it is highlighted that structured data significantly simplifies adherence to the FAIR principles compared to free text, which can be more complex and resource-intensive.

Question: Which of the Top 10 practices have you already applied?

Rich, detailed metadata descriptions and explicit licensing were the most applied practices by respondents (Fig. 18). Ethical considerations and

including the full set of references to any object required by the model (such as e.g., code libraries, environments, ...) seemed to be not yet applied by the majority of respondents.

Fig. 18 – Top 10 practices already applied

Question: Which of the Top 10 practices might you adopt in the future?

Respondents strongly highlighted the necessity of thoroughly documenting data requirements and evaluation results as essential for ensuring model reproducibility, robustness, and applicability across different contexts. This matched well with the essential practice of having persistent identifiers to index the shared model.

Fig. 19 - Top 10 practices for future adoption

Additional comments from respondents:

Detailed reporting of model performance, along with established guidelines, significantly enhances model robustness and comparison with other models.

Including performance is very useful, but many details should be considered as models are affected by small variations for example seed (values used to ensure consistency and variability in processes and models) used during training and applying identical sets of metrics may not be the most appropriate.

3.4.3 Open Discussion

The open discussion (second part of the online meeting) focused mainly on discussing tools and practices for verifying, documenting, and sharing AI models, particularly in relation to metadata and interoperability.

Participants shared diverse experiences and provided insights towards practical solutions and general challenges, as in the following:

- **Metadata Standards and Tools:** Participants highlighted HuggingFace as a valuable ecosystem, particularly emphasising its provision of a common API, that seems better implemented than its support for documentation. The HuggingFace API simplifies the reuse and interoperability of models across various applications, something that repositories (registries) in general do not achieve easily. In this way, the development effort needed by reusing a model is reduced and this kind of platform is suitable for developers seeking efficiency for reuse and testing, prioritising this over well-organised metadata.
- **Metadata standards:** The group agreed on the importance of having a minimal, standardised metadata schema. A critical observation was that while the technical implementation of metadata standards might be straightforward, achieving high-quality, widely-adopted metadata is primarily a social and "cultural" issue. A smaller number of universally agreed-upon metadata fields was suggested as the way forward, increasing the likelihood of broad adoption within the community. It is still an open question as to the kind of metadata to include (related to the model only, or also on the input data, perhaps metadata linked to model's evaluation, etc.).
- **Differentiating Data and Metadata:** related to the first point, a comment proposed distinguishing between the AI model itself (as "data") and its descriptive metadata. These two aspects present distinct challenges, particularly emphasising interoperability and practical usability challenges associated with storing, accessing, and deploying models from repositories, in contrast to a registry containing only metadata. Simply describing

models and making them accessible for practical use are two different worlds that would be useful to capture in one place.

- **End-to-end Metadata tracking:** The availability of open-source tools such as MLFlow, which enable capturing extensive metadata throughout the entire lifecycle of AI model development and deployment was mentioned. These tools allow detailed logging of the training parameters and performance metrics, thus enhancing transparency, reproducibility, and usability across diverse application domains.
- **Reproducibility and Containerisation:** Participants to the survey indicated Docker and containerisation as potential solutions for enhancing reproducibility, however, this did not reach consensus. Nevertheless, containerisation was considered by some participants as important to the discussion. It was noted that especially when combined with a standardised REST (representational state transfer) API, allowing users to interact seamlessly with deployed models. Containerisation alone was insufficient, and there is often the need for intermediary standards and layers of different codes to address broader interoperability challenges among diverse ML/AI models.
- **Automated Accessibility:** A point was made about machine accessibility of metadata, so that models could be automatically discovered, evaluated, and utilized by machines without human intervention. This automated accessibility was recognised as an ambitious yet desirable goal to achieve.

Overall, the meeting aimed to address challenges in metadata, interoperability, and reproducibility to improve the usability and accessibility of AI models. Despite low participation, valid points were raised and discussed, which enriched the results of the survey. It is hoped that this deliverable will provide a basis for further discussion and development of the ideas and key points that have emerged.

3.5 Conclusion and Outlook

Most of the ideas expressed through these Top 10 practices as voted on by members of the AI research community are reiterations of the FAIR principles

or implications of these as they apply to data. For example, being findable through PIDs, having “rich metadata” with broadly used formats, or providing appropriate licences. However, they also reflect the challenges facing researchers, because of the vast amounts of data, computational power and complex processes and specific conditions involved, and not least the impact AI models can have on society. It can be seen that refined, specific elaborations and interpretations of practices have been deemed important enough to include in the Top 10 at the expense of other seemingly more obvious ones. This is most obvious with respect to metadata: what it should contain and how it should be made accessible and available. Two further important practices emerged that go beyond traditional straightforward interpretation of FAIR, namely clear instructions on how to deploy the model and reporting of ethical considerations or analyses.

The motive behind working with the community to arrive at this Top 10 was that researchers could themselves determine/arrive at the practices they felt were most important and how feasible they could be to implement, as well as to provide avenues into the community for uptake (and refinement) of the Top 10 as far as possible. Possible approaches to this would be returning to those researchers and networks we originally contacted, as well as those with whom we have collaborated. In addition to FAIR4ML, there are other groups within the RDA focusing on FAIR and ethical considerations in AI. Other possibilities for uptake include identifying 10 key practices that specific AI application communities consider important to recommend and holding discussion with researchers to get more insights from a practical point of view.

While concrete implementation steps for many of these practices are outside the scope of the Top 10, initial reflections and discussions have started (e.g., defining a minimum set of metadata, or identifying features that a repository archiving ML models should ideally provide). The Top 10, along with the broader set of FAIR practices, offer useful insights into what is needed for implementation and serve as early-stage ideas for how to achieve it.

The results of the Delphi study were presented at the 19th edition of the International Digital Curation Conference (IDCC25) in The Hague, Netherlands between 17-19 February 2025 ([Osmenaj et al., 2025](#)). The presentation will be published as report in the related conference output as another way to promote and stimulate uptake of the recommended practices.

Acknowledgements

We would like to acknowledge the support and input of the FAIR4ML community through providing expert opinion as well as facilitating visibility to the Top 10 task through their regular IG meetings and at RDA Plenaries. We would of course also like to thank all participants in our study for sharing their expertise, opinions and time.

4 FAIR Data for Health Technology

4.1 Introduction

Task 6.3.3b called for the creation of a network of individuals interested in making Health Technology (HT) research data FAIR, evaluation of current FAIR data practices in HT and creation of recommendations for improving these. While there are several networks and communities around FAIR for Health data, for example Elixir nodes, the FAIR4Health project and new efforts such as the RDA Health Data Commons Global Open Research Commons Working Group, there is no community focusing on FAIR in HT as a domain. Granted, there are initiatives around FAIRifying bioinformatics, but this is only one area that may be considered either part of or related to HT. This is simultaneously surprising and understandable. Surprising, because the integration of technology in developing and testing therapies continues apace at leading research performing organisations worldwide. Understandable, because there is always a great deal of justified caution when it comes to health data or anything that could be considered health data. It is possible that lack of distinction for any number of reasons, between health data and “health technology data” has also been a factor. These complexities had significant effects on the task, as will be discussed below.

4.2 Methodology

As task 6.3.3b (FAIR & HT) was similar in some ways to task 6.3.3a (FAIR for AI), it made sense to see whether some of the strategies could be copied. Having a ready community and a small body of literature for FAIR in ML/AI, we led with that task aiming to subsequently implement successful strategies in FAIR and HT. Thus, while we proceeded with the literature review and survey item development for FAIR and AI, for HT we reached out to potential participants, clarified our understanding of HT research data and how broad or narrow our approach should be to ensure the best results, and carried out a literature search. Based on our definition of Health Technology research data: data which is collected, generated, analysed, and (re-)used during the

design, testing, and assessment of new technological devices and systems developed to solve a health problem and / or improve quality of lives, we carried out online searches using various string combinations including the words “FAIR”, “data”, “health”, “technology”, “research”, “network”, “community”. These searches returned many articles etc., on FAIR health data, and some on using technology to FAIRify health data, the advantages of implementing FAIR for health research, and so on, but there were no results pertaining to FAIR and health technology or health technology research. The literature collected is available in the Zotero library of the subtask [here](#).

There was also concern as to the data object that we would like to make FAIR. HT research takes place across different faculties and departments focusing on many different therapies and diagnostic tools. Comparing different artefacts would prove tricky, and it would be difficult, perhaps impossible, to standardise these. Eventually, in light of the above, the team decided to approach researchers at their respective institutions to see if we could converge upon a tangible “use-case” through which we could investigate FAIR data practices, with the hope that these could be extrapolated to other areas. After considering areas of precision medicine and rehabilitation robotics, the latter was chosen, as there appeared to be more accessible researchers and data professionals in this field. Having settled this, efforts commenced to recruit researchers and data professionals who would form a network initiative and support us with the evaluation and recommendation of FAIR practices in HT, at least in their area of focus.

4.2.1 BoF: FAIR for Prosthetics Design and Assessment

Introduction

As mentioned above, the evaluation of FAIR practices and the establishment of a network of people interested in this go hand in hand. In fact, the network initiative necessarily precede the discussion. The team continued to pursue a use-case in rehabilitation robotics. While this was happening, we gathered interest from a group of researchers centring around prosthetics design and assessment, based individually in Italy, Netherlands, the UK and the US . This

Title of the Document

presented an unmissable opportunity to initiate a network and begin the discussion with this area of research as a use-case, and an application to hold a [Birds of a Feather \(BoF\)](#) was submitted and approved for the Research Data Alliance (RDA) 22nd Virtual Plenary meeting on 14 May 2024. BoF sessions are held to gauge interest in a topic before progressing to a working or interest group in the RDA.

Objectives

The primary objectives of the BoF session were:

- To explore the application of the FAIR principles in prosthetics design and assessment.
- To discuss the rationale for creating an Interest Group within RDA for early adopters of FAIR in this domain.
- To identify possible objectives and future directions for this Interest Group.

Participation in the BoF was low, perhaps due to the combined effects of the specific topic title and a generally poorly attended plenary. Nevertheless, the session provided a solid foundation for future work in applying the FAIR principles to prosthetics design and assessment.

Presentations

Five speakers from diverse organizations and backgrounds were invited to share their work related to the FAIR principles in prosthetics design and assessment. The presentations covered various aspects of data collection, standardization, and analysis in the design process:

1. Data in User-Centred Prosthetics Design and Assessment
2. Consideration of User Needs
3. User-Centred Design in Prosthetics Technology Development
4. The Impact of Personalized Health Technology for Sustainable Healthcare

More details are described in the public [Collaborative Notes](#) of the BoF session.

Discussion

Following the presentations, a discussion was facilitated among the participants by using [Wooclap](#). The focus was on the rationale for establishing an Interest Group within RDA, potential objectives, and ways to move forward. Despite the specificity of the topic, the discussion yielded valuable insights.

Discussion and Takeaways

The adoption of standards and shared procedures in data collection for rehabilitation engineering, combined with standard benchmarking frameworks, would facilitate more reliable assessments of prosthetics solutions by enabling effective data sharing within the field. This group of researchers would hopefully form the core of a network initiative, with prosthetics and design assessment possibly serving as a use-case for examining the state of FAIR practices in HT, evaluating these practices and making recommendations, if needed.

Points raised during presentations and discussion were:

- **Recommendations for Researchers and Data Professionals:** guidelines on procedures and standardisation for data collection and use throughout the prosthetics design process
- **Resources:** A list of existing resources could be useful to support researchers in this field
- **Method Development:** Methods for data collection and analysis and the standardisation of assessment procedures were discussed.

Implications for the task

The establishment of an Interest Group within RDA could have been a crucial step in advancing these needs. Unfortunately, given the low number participants during the BoF, it was not possible to proceed further with the creation of an interest group within the RDA. However, the resources, discussion and participants were valuable in moving the work forward.

4.2.2 Survey on FAIR Data in Health Technology

4.2.2.1 Introduction

Following the BoF, other possibilities were explored towards bringing together a core group of interested parties to engage with the topic and to form the basis for a network. Close contact was maintained with BoF speakers with the intention to build around the rehabilitation robotics and /prosthetics design and assessment use-case. However, we decided to expand invitations for interest in general. Meetings were held with representatives of initiatives such as [Convergence](#) - a joint effort between TU Delft, Erasmus Medical Centre and Erasmus University Rotterdam in the Netherlands and institutions such as [SciLifeLab](#) in Sweden. Outreach to principal investigators, project leaders and researchers at institutions across Europe intensified. Exchanges were also held with representatives of Elixir nodes in attempts to establish whether a subset of their communities might be interested in our proposed network and contributing to the evaluation of and recommendations for FAIR practices in HT.

It proved extremely challenging to engage researchers and data professionals, who gave several reasons for their hesitation. These included the view that their data belonged either in technology, engineering etc., or within health data. Thus potential stakeholders felt that their domains were already being addressed by existing frameworks, and they were unsure about the need for yet another. Those working in bioinformatics felt similarly; they already had a well-established community that served them adequately.

The result of this was that with great effort we continued to gradually build a small group of interested individuals, but not with enough members within a particular use-case area to carry out meaningful evaluation of and recommendations for FAIR practices. The decision was taken therefore to carry out a survey to, on a more fundamental level, gather information on current knowledge application, and challenges about the FAIR principles in Health Technology research. This information would in turn be used to initiate a wider discussion on FAIR and HT research data, which could be the focus of a network of individuals interested in this. An output of this network

could be a report or paper comprising evaluation and recommendations on how the FAIR principles that could be commonly implemented across different areas of HT, with possible further refinements where applicable. For these, based on the outputs of the BoF session, a survey about the FAIR principles in Health Technology research was created and launched in March 2025, to gauge appetite for creating a group/ network related to FAIR data in Health Technology research (section 4.2.2).

4.2.2.2 Survey method and contents

In order to ensure maximum participation in the survey, promotional meetings were held with researchers and data professionals to remind, inform and update them about the task and the new directions and objectives. The survey was hosted on the EUSurvey platform. The statements/questions in the survey were based on the outputs of the May 2024 BoF session, see [Appendix V](#). After refinement and generalisation of these outputs, and promotional meetings with potential stakeholders, the survey was launched on 17 March 2025 and it remained open for 2 weeks.

4.2.2.3 Survey results

The survey was comprised of 3 main parts:

1. Participants Information
2. Awareness and application of the FAIR principles in Health Technology
3. Interest in any network/group/initiative in the field of FAIR data for Health Technology

I. Respondent Profile

We invited 20 researchers and data professionals to participate in the survey, and 16 responded. They were from 6 countries: Italy (5), Netherlands (4), Sweden (3), Belgium (1), Spain (1), Slovakia (1), United States (1) (Fig. 20).

Fig. 20 - Geographical distribution of participants

11 were associated with academic institutions, while 5 were associated with research institutions.

Fig. 21 - Participant's type of institution

Roles varied, but data-centric and research support roles dominated the sample: Data Professionals (7), Postdoctoral Candidates (3), Research Scientists: (3), Associate Professors (1), Technician/Research Assistant (1), Technical Platform Operator (1) (Fig. 22).

Fig. 22 - Distribution of roles among participants

A wide range of career stages were represented, especially Mid-career professionals (56,2%), Senior professionals (18,8%), Early-career (18,8%), Other/unspecified (6,2%) (Fig. 23).

Fig. 23 - Career stages of participants

II. Awareness and Adoption of FAIR Principles

Familiarity with the FAIR Principles

The survey revealed high awareness: Familiar with FAIR (87,5%), Heard of but not familiar (12,5%), Never heard of: 0 (Fig. 24).

Fig. 24 - Familiarity with the FAIR principles

Implementation of the FAIR principles in Practice

When asked about application of the FAIR principles, only a minority believed they apply the FAIR principles extensively, with 50% indicating partial or neutral adoption. This highlights a gap between awareness as highlighted above and practical implementation. Large extent: 7; Somewhat: 4; Neutral: 4; Small extent: 1 (Fig. 25).

Fig. 25 - Application of the FAIR principles in research activities

Use of Standards and Best Practices

Respondents were asked if they follow community standards when managing research data. Half of the respondents reported alignment with standardisation efforts, with the other half reporting partial or no conscious effort in alignment (Fig. 26).

Fig. 26 - Use of standards or any community-endorsed practices

Use of Protocols and Tools

Results similar to those in use of standards and best practices emerged in relation to protocols and tools: Yes (7), Partly (6), No (3) (Fig. 27).

Fig. 27 - Use of protocols and tools in research activities

Role in the Health Technology workflow

Respondents were actively involved across multiple stages of the technology development workflow (Fig. 28).

Fig. 28 - Involvement of the respondents across the different stages of the design workflow

III. Willingness to Join a FAIR Working Group/Network in FAIR for HT

Participants were asked whether they would join a working group or network in the field of FAIR for Health Technology and the results showed a strong level of interest (Fig. 29).

Fig. 29 - Willingness to join a group/ network in FAIR for HT research

4.3 Discussion

Among our 16 survey participants, we observed a wide spread of geographical location in Europe, range of roles (both researchers and professionals), and stage of career. This suggests that the views expressed via the survey could be taken as a meaningful model of real experiences.

All respondents had heard of the FAIR principles, and it was encouraging to see that almost all were familiar with them. Disparity begins to emerge, however, with response to questions of implementation of the FAIR principles, use of standards and best practices, protocols and tools. Across these three areas, less than half of respondents answered that they implemented and used these, with the rest doing so only partially or not at

all. It is also interesting to note that there is a reasonably good spread of involvement across the different design workflow processes for health technologies. In short, this suggests that while there is high awareness of the FAIR principles, there is only middling implementation of strategies to support their application. There may be several reasons for this, however, two main ones could be suggested. Firstly, as with AI, there might be various distinct efforts to implement the FAIR principles, but no general, simple-to-use guidelines. Second, there may be a lack of metrics for gauging the quality and robustness of practices aimed at FAIR implementation. Aside from the clear needs implied, the results of this survey support the timeliness of this task, and also indicates a way forward. 15 out of 16 participants expressed some level of interest in joining a network for FAIR data in Health Technology, and there is clearly work to be done.

4.4 Conclusion and Next Steps

As technology advances, and with increasing use of AI, the use of technology in diagnosis, development of therapies and health research in general will only increase. This puts both HT research and FAIR data efforts at an important juncture, underlining the timeliness and importance of this task. However, as mentioned earlier in this report, the prospect of evaluating and recommending FAIR practices in Health Technology in the absence of relevant literature and a relevant community was a challenging one. This was indeed borne out during the course of the project, necessitating taking a step back and looking at more fundamental questions to form a basis for broad discussion and subsequent refinement. It is impossible to disentangle the development of best practices and the community to which it applies, since it is the community members themselves who would need to discuss develop, agree upon and implement these practices.

Hopefully, the insights gathered through this survey can be harnessed as a starting point and vehicle of focus for a nascent network. A framework for this could be to build a [FAIR Implementation Profile](#) aligned with a Health Technology Design Workflow. An important first step could include a

community definition for Health Technology Data. The task team offer the following definition, which can be amended to suit:

Health Technology data can be defined as “data which is collected, generated, analysed, and used during the design, testing, and assessment of technological devices and systems developed to solve a health problem and/or improve quality of lives”.

A serendipitous development during the run-up to the survey was the [TEF Health Project](#), part of which is a work package looking at FAIRness, standardisation, preprocessing, etc., in Health AI and robotics research. At the same time, a network initiative focusing on FAIR data in precision medicine at SciLifeLab is currently under consideration. By the end of the Skills4EOSC project on 31 August 2025, we aim to have at least two meetings with those survey participants who expressed interest in a FAIR and HT network to share and discuss the survey findings and further discuss the formation of a network initiative. We have invited colleagues at SciLifeLab and those working in the TEF Health project to collaborate on such a network. This will ensure the network initiative continues beyond Skills4EOSC, hopefully providing support and structure for progress in FAIR data in Health Technology.

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Appendix I. The list of 20 recommended practices to vote for in Round 1 of Delphi Survey (FAIR and AI)

Recommended best practice to vote (definition)	More information/description on the best practice (description)
1. ML/AI models should be trained on FAIR data.	To increase FAIRness of an ML/AI model, training data should be thoroughly documented and made FAIR themselves.
2. Globally unique Persistent Identifiers should be assigned to ML/AI models and included in their metadata.	For instance, a DOI should be assigned to the ML/AI model and its metadata to make it findable for both humans and machines via indexing in searchable resources. In the case of model updates, new identifiers must be generated to distinguish the updated versions from the original.
3. ML/AI models should be described with rich metadata.	Rich metadata (descriptive keywords, contextual information, etc.) enhances findability and reuse.
4. Metadata for ML/AI models should remain accessible even when the ML/AI model is no longer accessible.	This ensures long-term preservation and accessibility of metadata, even when the ML/AI model is no longer available.
5. ML/AI models and their metadata should be retrievable through persistent identifiers using a standardised communications protocol that is open, free, and universally implementable.	This enables the ML/AI model to be discovered by humans and machines, to be downloaded or directly invoked to conduct AI inference, enabling accessibility. Where necessary, the protocol should allow for an authentication and authorization procedure.
6. Standard metadata schemas and standard-compliant APIs should be used to make the ML/AI model interoperable with other models.	The ML/AI model interoperates with other models, data, and/or software by exchanging data and/or metadata, and/or through interaction via application programming interfaces (APIs), described through standards.
7. ML/AI models should be hosted on a dedicated online repository ensuring findability, accessibility, and interoperability.	The availability of standardized application programming interfaces (APIs) can enable machine-actionability.
8. ML/AI models should be made available also as platform-independent and general representation to enable interoperability and reuse.	There are efforts that use extensible computation graph models to represent ML/AI models built with different frameworks. With a platform-independent computational graph representation, ML/AI models developed with different frameworks can be transferred to a general format, and hence support

	interoperability between frameworks.
9. The ML/AI model's metadata should report evaluation results, e.g. accuracy, precision, recall, train vs. test error, etc	Specify your model's evaluation results in a structured way in the ML/AI model metadata.
10. ML/AI Models should be containerized to enhance interoperability and reuse.	By leveraging containers, the ML/AI application can be deployed and executed on any infrastructure that supports containerization, regardless of the underlying Operating System.
11. ML/AI model metadata should document any prerequisite on the input data format and structure, including any required pre-processing, and output data format.	If the referred training data is altered through pre-processing steps or there is a post-processing of the output of the model, this must be noted and described in the metadata for the model to promote transparency and reuse-options.
12. ML/AI model metadata should use a documented, accessible, and ideally broadly used format.	As with metadata for other outputs, the metadata for ML/AI models should be in standardised format that is accessible for either humans or machines.
13. ML/AI model metadata should include the scope and known limitations to support responsible reuse in other contexts.	For instance, it would be desirable to highlight known biases at all steps of the ML workflow.
14. ML/AI model metadata should include qualified references to any related/required research objects, including code libraries, environments, code dependencies etc.	Qualified references should be made available following standards of either globally unique persistent identifiers, or using best practice to refer to code libraries.
15. ML/AI models should read, write and exchange data in a way that meets domain-relevant community standards.	The model's operations should comply with the standards accepted in the particular domain in which the model is applied to achieve interoperability and reusability. For example, a healthcare-applicable ML/AI model should accept data represented in standard healthcare data formats.
16. ML/AI models should have clear and accessible licences attached to them.	Clearly stated licensing terms are important for reusability of the ML/AI model. For instance, Open Responsible AI Licenses (Open RAIL) are licenses designed to permit free and open access, re-use, and downstream distribution of derivatives of AI artifacts.
17. Any ethical considerations/analyses during model development should be reported.	For instance, external review / ethical approval.

<p>18. AI/ML models should be associated with detailed provenance information, ideally by adding metadata referring to a specific ML-provenance language and including information about decision-making process for method selection.</p>	<p>Provenance information ensures the reproducibility of the AI/ML models. Provenance information from the data harvesting, learning data preparation and learning for the model should be captured in an ML specific provenance language that allows for the caption of ML specific aspects. For example, PROV-ML can be used as a specific language capturing ML-related provenance.</p>
<p>19. Clear instructions on how to deploy the ML/AI model should be provided.</p>	<p>Deployment instructions ensures that users can effectively utilize the model in various environments, thus enhancing reproducibility.</p>
<p>20. Model lineage should be ensured by documenting that this model (version) in production is the output of a specific execution of ML/AI source code with specified hyperparameters and metrics.</p>	<p>This practice provides a comprehensive understanding of the model's origins and performance, making it easier for others to validate and reuse the model effectively.</p>

Appendix II. List of practices to vote for in Round 2 of Delphi survey (FAIR and AI)

LIST OF PRACTICES FROM ROUND 1, TO RE-VOTE FOR IN ROUND 2	DESCRIPTION
<p>Practice N.1: ML/AI models should be trained on FAIR data.</p>	<p>Whenever possible, to increase FAIRness of a ML/AI model, training data should be FAIR themselves, ensuring they are machine actionable and thoroughly documented, as a pre-requisite for data quality. Using FAIR data to train models ensures higher reproducibility, increases reliability, trustworthiness, and transparency. We recall that FAIR does not mean "open" (e.g. sensitive datasets can be FAIR, without being open).</p>
<p>Practice N.2: Globally Unique Persistent Identifiers should be assigned to ML/AI models and included in their metadata.</p>	<p>For instance, a DOI (or other type of globally persistent and unique identifier) should be assigned to the ML/AI model to make it findable for both humans and machines via indexing in searchable resources: this would increase the model's findability. In the case of model updates, new identifiers could be generated to distinguish the updated versions from the original.</p>
<p>Practice N.5: ML/AI models and their metadata should be retrievable through persistent identifiers using a standardised communications protocol that is open, free, and universally implementable.</p>	<p>This practice would enable ML/AI model's accessibility through standard, widely adopted tools. Where necessary, the protocol should allow for an authentication and authorization procedure.</p>
<p>Practice N.13: ML/AI model metadata should include the scope and known limitations to support responsible reuse in other contexts.</p>	<p>For instance, it would be desirable to report in the metadata - possibly in a structured and standard way - available information on the appropriate use/reuse of the model, also by highlighting known biases and constraints, as well as contextual information about training.</p>
<p>Practice N.14: ML/AI model metadata should include qualified references to any related/required research objects, including code libraries, environments, code dependencies etc.</p>	<p>Qualified references should be made available in the metadata using references to globally unique persistent identifiers, as well as in the documentation using best practices to link code libraries. Moreover, it would be recommended to use semantics to define the relationships among different elements in the model workflow. This would ensure maximum reusability, reproducibility, and collaboration in the development and deployment of AI models.</p>

<p>Practice N.17: Any ethical considerations/analyses during model development should be reported.</p>	<p>There should be proactive consideration of possible bias, discrimination, known limitations in AI systems which can perpetuate unfair outcomes and hinder inclusivity. Privacy, security, and surveillance concerns need to be addressed to protect individuals' rights.</p>
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<p>ADDITIONAL PRACTICES to vote for in Round 2 (suggested by participants during Round 1)</p>	<p>PRACTICE DESCRIPTION</p>
<p>Practice A.1: References to all datasets (including versioning) used for training, validation, and testing of the ML/AI model must be included in the ML/AI model's metadata, via their Global Persistent and Unique Identifiers.</p>	<p>Include PIDs for each dataset in the model's metadata.</p>
<p>Practice A.2: Model's metadata should include all information needed to fully reproduce the results, including (but not limited to) parameters like random number generator seed, hardware specifications, etc.</p>	<p>To make the AI/ML model reproducible, you should include different details on metadata like: model parameters, training environment, training process, information on the dataset etc.</p>
<p>Practice A.3: The ML/AI model and related datasets should comply with privacy protection laws and regulation: metadata should provide information on caveats for use and any warnings about unintended violations of privacy laws which may result from the use of the model.</p>	<p>Provide through metadata information related to specific conditions on usage, and potential risks that could arise from the use of the AI /ML model.</p>
<p>Practice A.4: Metadata schemas for ML/AI models should make use of standard or ad hoc ontologies.</p>	<p>Metadata schemas for ML/AI models should or must incorporate established or widely-used ontologies. These ontologies, whether formal standards or created for specific tasks, provide a structured way to define and classify data, ensuring better organization, understanding, and interoperability of the models and their components. Using standard or well-defined ontologies helps improve consistency and clarity when describing and sharing ML/AI models.</p>
<p>Practice A.5: Reporting of the ML process should follow community-backed guidelines and recommendations, and provide the utilities/tools to convert data between the platform-specific</p>	<p>By adhering to these community-backed guidelines, your report is clear, detailed, and easy for others in the community to replicate or understand, ensuring a higher level of</p>

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format if applicable.	transparency and reproducibility.
Practice A.6: A sample FAIR dataset to be used with/test the model should be provided.	In the literature exist several publicly available FAIR compliant datasets that can be used to develop/test the AI/ML model to ensure responsible reuse and adherence to community standards.

Appendix III. List of Top 10 best practices for FAIR implementation in ML/AI (Delphi study result)

a: (Practice N. 2 - Consensus reached in Round 2)

Definition: Globally Unique Persistent Identifiers should be assigned to ML/AI models and included in their metadata.

Description: For instance, a DOI (or other type of globally persistent and unique identifier) should be assigned to the ML/AI model to make it findable for both humans and machines via indexing in searchable resources: this would increase the model's findability. In the case of model updates, new identifiers could be generated to distinguish the updated versions from the original.

b: (Practice N. 3 - Consensus reached in Round 1)

Definition: ML/AI models should be described with rich metadata.

Description: Rich metadata (descriptive keywords, contextual information, etc.) enhances findability and reuse.

c: (Practice N. 5 - Consensus reached in Round 2)

Definition: ML/AI models and their metadata should be retrievable through persistent identifiers using a standardised communications protocol that is open, free, and universally implementable.

Description: This practice would enable ML/AI model's accessibility through standard, widely adopted tools. Where necessary, the protocol should allow for an authentication and authorization procedure.

d: (Practice N. 9 - Consensus reached in Round 1)

Definition: The ML/AI model's metadata should report evaluation results, e.g. accuracy, precision, recall, train vs. test error, etc.

Description: Specify your model's evaluation results in a structured way in

the ML/AI model metadata.

e: (Practice N. 11 - Consensus reached in Round 1)

Definition: ML/AI model metadata should document any prerequisite on the input data format and structure, including any required pre-processing, and output data format.

Description: If the referred training data is altered through pre-processing steps or there is a post-processing of the output of the model, this must be noted and described in the metadata for the model to promote transparency and reuse-options.

f: (Practice N. 12 - Consensus reached in Round 1)

Definition: ML/AI model metadata should use a documented, accessible, and ideally broadly used format.

Description: As with metadata for other outputs, the metadata for ML/AI models should be in standardised format that is accessible for either humans or machines.

g: (Practice N.14 - Consensus reached in Round 2)

Definition: ML/AI model metadata should include qualified references to any related/required research objects, including code libraries, environments, code dependencies etc.

Description: Qualified references should be made available in the metadata using references to globally unique persistent identifiers, as well as in the documentation using best practices to link code libraries. Moreover, it would be recommended to use semantics to define the relationships among different elements in the model workflow. This would ensure maximum reusability, reproducibility, and collaboration in the development and deployment of AI models.

h: (Practice N. 16 - Consensus reached in Round 1)

Definition: ML/AI models should have clear and accessible licenses

attached to them.

Description: Clearly stated licensing terms are important for reusability of the ML/AI model. For instance, Open Responsible AI Licenses (Open RAIL) are licenses designed to permit free and open access, re-use, and downstream distribution of derivatives of AI artifacts.

i: (Practice N.17 - Consensus reached in Round 2)

Definition: Any ethical considerations/analyses during model development should be reported.

Description: There should be proactive consideration of possible bias, discrimination, known limitations in AI systems which can perpetuate unfair outcomes and hinder inclusivity. Privacy, security, and surveillance concerns need to be addressed to protect individuals' rights.

j: (Practice N. 19 - Consensus reached in Round 1)

Definition: Clear instructions on how to deploy the ML/AI model should be provided.

Description: Deployment instructions ensures that users can effectively utilize the model in various environments, thus enhancing reproducibility.

Appendix IV. List of practices eliminated from Delphi study (FAIR and AI)

Practice definition	Delphi round where it was excluded
Practice N.1: ML/AI models should be trained on FAIR data.	Round 2
Practice N.4: Metadata for ML/AI models should remain accessible even when the ML/AI model is no longer accessible.	Round 1
Practice N. 6: Standard metadata schemas and standard-compliant APIs should be used to make the ML/AI model interoperable with other models.	Round 1
Practice N.7: ML/AI models should be hosted on a dedicated online repository ensuring findability, accessibility, and interoperability.	Round 1
Practice N.8: ML/AI models should be made available also as platform-independent and general representation to enable interoperability and reuse.	Round 1
Practice N.10: ML/AI Models should be containerized to enhance interoperability and reuse.	Round 1
Practice N.13: ML/AI model metadata should include the scope and known limitations to support responsible reuse in other contexts.	Round 2
Practice N.15: ML/AI models should read, write and exchange data in a way that meets domain-relevant community standards.	Round 1
Practice N.18: AI/ML models should be associated with detailed provenance information, ideally by adding metadata referring to a specific ML-provenance language and including information about decision-making process for method selection.	Round 1
Practice N. 20: Model lineage should be ensured by documenting that this model (version) in production is the output of a specific execution of ML/AI source code with specified hyperparameters and metrics.	Round 1
Practice A.1: References to all datasets (including versioning) used for training, validation, and testing of the ML/AI model must be included in the ML/AI model's metadata, via their Global Persistent and Unique Identifiers.	Round 2

Practice A.2: Model's metadata should include all information needed to fully reproduce the results, including (but not limited to) parameters like random number generator seed, hardware specifications, etc.	Round 2
Practice A.3: The ML/AI model and related datasets should comply with privacy protection laws and regulation: metadata should provide information on caveats for use and any warnings about unintended violations of privacy laws which may result from the use of the model.	Round 2
Practice A.4: Metadata schemas for ML/AI models should make use of standard or ad hoc ontologies.	Round 2
Practice A.5: Reporting of the ML process should follow community-backed guidelines and recommendations, and provide the utilities/tools to convert data between the platform-specific format if applicable.	Round 2
Practice A.6: A sample FAIR dataset to be used with/test the model should be provided.	Round 2

Appendix V. Health Technology survey questions

Part 1: Participants information

* Name

* Surname

* Email

* Country

* Which type of institution do you work in?

Adapted from State of Open Data 2024

- University
- Medical School
- Research Institution
- National Government / Local Government
- Private Company
- Hospital
- Other (please specify answering the next question)

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* What is the name of your institution? Please write the ROR ID as reported in [ROR registry](#).

[Example: ROR ID of the Italian Institute of Technology is: <https://ror.org/042t93s57>.]

* Which of the following roles best applies to you?

Adapted from State of Open Data 2024.

- Professor
- Associate professor
- Assistant Professor
- Physician/Clinician
- Healthcare professional
- Laboratory Director/Head
- PhD/Masters Student
- Postdoctoral candidate
- Principal Investigator
- Research Director/VP of Research
- Research Scientist
- Undergraduate Student
- Technician/Research Assistant
- Data Professional
- Other

* If "other", please write your role title here

* Career stage

Early-career: Typically ranges from 0 to 5 years of experience. This stage includes entry-level positions and the initial few years of professional experience.

Mid-career: Generally ranges from 5 to 15 years of experience. At this stage, professionals often have a significant amount of experience, possibly including managerial responsibilities or specialized expertise.

Senior: Usually includes 15+ years of experience. Senior professionals often hold high-level positions with substantial responsibility, leadership roles, or deep expertise in their field.

- Early-career
- Mid-career
- Senior
- Other (please specify below)

* If "other", please specify your career stage here

Part 2: FAIR principles in Health Technology research field

This part contains a list of questions related to the state of the art of the FAIR principles in your research.

* How familiar are you with the FAIR data principles?

Adapted from State of Open Data 2021.

- I am familiar with the FAIR data principles
- I have previously heard of the FAIR data principles but I am not familiar with them
- I have never heard of the FAIR data principles before now

This field is required.

* To what extent do you think you make your data FAIR?

Adapted from State of Open Data 2021.

- A large extent
- Somewhat
- Neutral
- A small extent
- Not at all
- I don't know

This field is required.

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* **Health Technology Research data** can be regarded as "data which is collected, generated, analysed, and (re-)used during the design, testing, and assessment of new technological devices and systems developed to solve a health problem and / or improve quality of lives".

Consider the above definition of Health Technology Research data. Does this correspond to your definition, or your understanding of this matter?

- Yes
- No
- Partly

* At which stage of the design workflow of technologies for Health / Health Technologies, are you primarily involved? The different stages are illustrated in the image below.

Image title: DATA in the prosthetics design process. Author: Maria Fossati.

- Ideation
- Prototype
- Test
- Use
- Implementation
- Assessment
- Other

This field is required.

* When you manage data during your research work, do you usually refer to any standards or community-endorsed practices?

- Yes
- No
- Partly

* During your research work, do you usually refer to any standards for protocols, procedures or tools?

- Yes
- No
- Partly

* What are the main difficulties / challenges in your opinion to apply standards in data management?

* Do you see any benefits to making your data FAIR, as far as may be possible? Please list and elaborate on these.

Part 3: Interest in joining any group/network/initiative in the field of FAIR data for Health Technology

In this part of the survey, you can express your interest or optionally recommend any group/network/project that could be interesting to join.

* Would you be interested in taking part in an interest / working group or network on making Health Technology data FAIR?

- Yes
- No
- I would need more information

What should be the main goal of this group / network?

Do you know any other group/initiative/network relevant for this topic?

If yes, please provide here any suggestion.